

Exploring the requirements for charging infrastructure for electrical heavy-goods vehicles with agent-based modelling

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Summary

Electric heavy-goods vehicles (e-HGVs) are vital for emission reduction and combating climate change. However, their adoption presents challenges with uncertainties in both behavioural and technical aspects. In this research study, we build an agent-based model to explore the infrastructure required to charge e-HGVs at a hypothetical service station given behavioural assumptions. Our prototype model considers drivers' potential charging behaviour, charger power levels, battery capacities, and truck driving regulations. Through experiments, our preliminary model demonstrates how reducing the number of fast chargers affects the charging system's performance. The insights from this model, once uncertainties have been constrained, could be valuable in supporting the design of a charging network nationwide, thus contributing to more effective emission reduction strategies in the UK.

KEYWORDS: Electric heavy-goods vehicles, charging infrastructure, agent-based modelling

1. Introduction to guidelines

Road transport constitutes one-fifth of global greenhouse gas emissions (Santos, 2017), with a third attributed to road freight transport (Ge and Friedrich, 2020). Heavy Goods Vehicles (HGVs) account for less than 5% of road vehicles in the EU, but are responsible for about a quarter of the total CO2 emissions from road transport (Danese et al., 2021). Electrifying heavy-duty vehicles emerges as a promising solution to address climate concerns and promote sustainable logistics. To significantly mitigate greenhouse gas emissions in road freight transport through electrification, widespread deployment of electric HGVs is imperative (Shoman et al., 2023, Al-Hanahi et al., 2021).

The widespread adoption of electric heavy-goods vehicles (e-HGVs) depends on the development of a robust charging station network. This network must provide sufficient coverage and meet the specific charging requirements of these vehicles along their travel routes (Speth et al., 2022). Studies indicate that existing charging stations are designed for personal cars and, as such, might be insufficient for meeting the charging requirements of e-HGVs. The larger batteries and extended travel ranges of e-HGVs present distinct challenges for the current infrastructure (Danese et al., 2021) for private cars.

This study focuses on investigating the benefits of providing charging infrastructure specifically designed for e-HGVs, using the Agent-Based Modelling (ABM) approach. ABM provides a dynamic and flexible framework, enabling the simulation of interactions among vehicles, charging infrastructure, and user behaviours (Menter et al., 2023, Karlsson and Grauers, 2023). By employing ABM, we aim to unravel the complexities related to vehicle arrivals, charging behaviour, and the availability of charging infrastructure. The synthetic population of agents, each representing a hypothetical, unique electric heavy-duty vehicle, allows for a detailed analysis of charging

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requirements, mirroring the diverse real-world scenarios encountered by e-HGVs.

Currently the model is based on a hypothetical publicly accessible parking site and employs numerous assumptions regarding truck flow rates and possible driver behaviours, but as more robust data become available in later stages of the project, these assumptions can begin to be informed by sound empirical evidence. Additionally, more complex behaviours will be developed to increase the realism of the model in later stages. Through this exploration, we aim to provide a more realistic and adaptable perspective on the design of charging network for e-HGVs across the UK.

2. Methods

2.1 Assumptions and environment

The proposed Agent-Based Model (ABM) is implemented using Netlogo, deploying a hypothetical, synthetic population of agents that represent individual e-HGVs. Each vehicle is defined by specific attributes, including battery capacity, arrival State of Charge (SoC), and arrival trip time (an estimated length of time that the driver has been driving for). In the preliminary experiments outlined below it is assumed that the arrival SoC of vehicles has a random value ranging from 10% to 70%, and the arrival trip time varies between 0.5 and 5 hours, although these assumptions will be refined as the project evolves. Additionally, e-HGVs are equipped with either a 250 kWh or 550 kWh battery pack (these are most the commonly available configurations).

It is further assumed that drivers require a mandatory break of at least 45 minutes after a maximum of 4.5 hours of continuous driving to align with the regulations outlined in Regulation (EC) No 561/2006 of the European Union (Menter et al., 2023). The charging station is equipped with three types of chargers: ultra-fast (1000 kw), fast (350 kw), and slow (150 kw) (in subsequent versions, we will retain the slow charger for overnight charging but not for daytime charging). Additionally, a dedicated parking area without charging facilities is also integrated.

2.2 Model development

Given the absence of comprehensive empirical charging data for e-HGVs, we simulate the charging behaviour of future e-HGVs based on the following assumptions. It is important to note that these current behaviours are experimental and the research does not yet attempt to ground them in real behavioural data.

To model operational behaviour, we simulate vehicle arrivals at the charging station and do not, yet, consider the journey to and from the station. Upon arrival and taking into consideration the arrival SoC and trip time, the following conditions are considered: a) drivers stop for charging without requiring a break, b) drivers stop for a break without charging, and c) drivers both need to charge and take a break. In a) and c), the driver will initiate charging immediately if chargers are available, prioritizing the fastest charger. Alternatively, they may join a queue (if space is available) and wait for chargers or choose to continue driving if no queue space is available.

For vehicles stopping only for charging, they either initiate charging immediately or join a queue, with the assumption that a charging cycle must end with a minimum SoC of 80%. For vehicles stopping for a break, we consider the possibility of opportunity charging if available chargers are found. For vehicles utilizing opportunity charging, if the SoC reaches 100% but there is insufficient break time, they move to a parking space or continue driving (in subsequent versions we will implement a system where vehicles will not move until they have completed their break as this more closely aligns with current regulations). Alternatively, they simply take a break at the parking space if all the chargers are in use.

For vehicles halting for both charging and a break, they either join a queue or initiate charging immediately. If the SoC reaches 100% but they still require extra time for their break then they move

to an available parking space or drive off (again, in subsequent versions vehicles will remain on the charger until they have completed their break). In cases where the break time exceeds 45 minutes, but the SoC remains below 80%, the vehicles continue charging until the SoC reaches up to 80%.

3. Preliminary results

To assess the charging station's performance, taking into account metrics such as average time in queue, average charging time, charger utilization, average dwell time, and the proportion of unserved vehicles, we vary the number of fast chargers. The experiment is implemented using pynetlogo as a wrapper around the NetLogo model to permit Monte-Carlo analysis. In scenario 1, a total of 15 chargers are deployed, with 5 of each of the three types. In scenario 2, the total number of chargers is reduced to 7, keeping the number of slow chargers the same as in scenario 1, while both the number of ultra-fast chargers and fast chargers are reduced to 1 (in subsequent versions, we will retain the slow charger for overnight charging but not for daytime charging).

Figure 1 shows the distributions of the five output metrics of interest. It is notable that the average time in queue increases to 2 hours when the number of fast chargers is reduced from 10 to 2. Additionally, the average charging time doubles from approximately 30 minutes to one hour. In scenario 1, about 65% of chargers are not fully utilized, while in scenario 2, the chargers are consistently in full use. Notably, the average dwell time escalates from 30 minutes to 3 hours. Regarding the proportion of unserved vehicles (those that decide to leave the site without charging), approximately 20% of vehicles cannot be served when the number of fast chargers is reduced to 2. As discussed, these preliminary results are not yet sufficiently robust for application to policy, but they demonstrate how a model such as this might be used once the behavioural (and other) assumptions have been refined.

Figure 1 Distribution of the outputs. (a) Scenario 1; (b) Scenario 2.

4. Discussion

In this study, we have developed a parsimonious agent-based model as a first step to estimating the charging infrastructure requirements for e-HGVs under uncertain parameters and driver behaviours. Our model simulates factors such as truck arrival rates, charger types, trip times, and compliance with truck driving regulations. However, it is crucial to acknowledge this study is an initial exploration, with several assumptions made, particularly regarding charging behavior and arrival rates, which will impact the accuracy of the results. Future research could address these limitations by collecting comprehensive data on e-HGV travel schedules and investigating the impact of diverse charging behaviors on factors such as SoC and the duration until drivers require a break. The outcomes of our study provide valuable insights for strategically planning and deploying charging infrastructure for e-HGVs engaged in long-haul operations.

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6. References

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Biographies

Dr Jiang is a research associate at the Alan Turing Institute since August 2023. She completed her PhD in Transportation Engineering in 2022 at Monash University, Australia, concentrated on employing

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Dr Malleson is a Professor of Spatial Science at the Centre for Spatial Analysis and Policy at the School of Geography, University of Leeds, UK. He has a PhD in Geography and undergraduate degrees in Computer Science (BSc) and Multidisciplinary Informatics (MSc). Most of his research focuses on the development of spatial computer models that help to understand and explain social phenomena. He has a particular interest in simulations of crime patterns, and in models that can be used to describe the flows of people around cities. More recently, he has become interested in how 'big data', agent-based modelling, and smart cities initiatives can be used to better understand the daily dynamics of cities and reduce the impacts of phenomena such as pollution or crime.

Mark Birkin is Professor of Spatial Analysis and Policy at the University of Leeds and Programme Director for Urban Analytics at the Alan Turing Institute, the UK's National Institute for Data Science and Artificial Intelligence. He has major domain interests in geodemographics, mathematical modelling and microsimulation.